

Right Hemi Maxillectomy Indicated for an Adenoid Cyst Carcinoma of the Palate with Intra Sinus Extension Operated on at the University Clinics of Kinshasa/DRC, Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery¹

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Abstract

Introduction: Cystic adenoid carcinomas, formerly known as cylindromas, are malignant epithelial tumours of the accessory salivary glands. They are generally slow-growing tumours that generally affect the 40 to 60 age group, without gender preponderance, and their preferred site is the hard palate. The risk factor is not well known. Dental surgeons receive very little training in this diagnosis, which means that it is often made very late and the extent of the lesions is considerable.

Observations: Patient aged 65, transferred from a hospital in the provincial city of Kinshasa to the University Clinics of Kinshasa, Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery for a documented cystic adenoid carcinoma of the palate. The functional signs were dysphagia, dysphonia and dyspnoea. The exo-oral examination was marked by a deformity of the right hemi-face that was painful to palpation, right nasal obstruction, right palpebral oedema, loss of sensitivity of the right hemi-face, and clinical absence of adenopathy. The endobuccal examination revealed a fleshy, budding mass approximately 5*3 cm in diameter occupying the hard palate and extending to the soft palate. Surgery consisted of a right hemi-maxillectomy plus a maxillofacial obturator prosthesis.

Discussion: The presentation of this clinical case is particularly linked to the slow, insidious, painless course of the disease, but also to the particular way in which adenoid cystic carcinoma extends to the palate. The lack of early diagnosis by dentists explains the frequent delay in diagnosis. Initial T4 stages account for more than 75% of cases, as was the case in our presentation, but lymph node metastases and distant metastases are also rare at the time of diagnosis, and in fact we did not find any satellite lymph nodes. Treatment consisted of surgery (hemi-maxillectomy) plus fitting of a maxillofacial obturator prosthesis.

Conclusion: This case shows that a delay in consultation, misdiagnosis, neglect or poor management of adenoid cystic carcinoma can be at the root of progression to a more advanced stage of the disease, which may also require more complex and difficult management, especially in a context of poverty such as ours.

Keywords

Cystic Adenoid Carcinoma, Palate, Surgery, Obturator Prosthesis.

Introduction

Cystic adenoid carcinomas (CAK), formerly known as cylindromas, are malignant epithelial tumours that generally grow slowly and develop in the facial region, most often at the expense of the accessory salivary glands [1]. Despite its slow evolution, it remains an aggressive malignant tumour with a guarded prognosis [2]. The disease mainly affects patients aged between 40 and 60, with no gender preponderance. It is the second most common type of salivary gland tumour [3]. Diagnosis of these tumours is difficult because they are rare and do not represent the same risk factors as squamous cell carcinoma, which alone accounts for 95% of malignant tumours of the oral cavity [4]. Dental surgeons receive very little training in this diagnosis, which means that it is often made very late and the extent of the lesions is considerable.

Observations

The case presented was that of a 65-year-old patient transferred from a hospital in the provincial city of Kinshasa to the Clinique's Universities de Kinshasa, Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, for a documented cystic adenoid carcinoma of the palate. In terms of medical and surgical history, the patient was known to be hypertensive and was being monitored, having already undergone 3 consecutive operations for this tumour without success. No allergies are known. The patient told us that the history of his illness dated back more than 15 years to the time of his current consultation, with the appearance of a small painless swelling on the hard palate which gradually increased in size until it reached a significant volume, prompting him to seek medical attention.

Figure 1: Exo buccal view

Figure 2: Endo-buccal view

He underwent three consecutive operations in 2020, 2021 and 2022 without success, and a histological examination in 2022 confirmed a CAK of the palate, from where he was transferred to the CUK for a MEPC. On physical examination, we noted that he was suffering from weight loss, dysphagia, dysphonia and dyspnoea. On exo-oral examination we noted a deformity marked by swelling of the right hemi-face that was painful on palpation, right nasal obstruction, right palpebral oedema, loss of sensitivity of the

right hemi-face, and clinical absence of adenopathy (Figure 1). On endobuccal examination, we noted a mouth opening of 3 fingerbreadths, defective oral hygiene, edentulism from 16 to 18, IV degree mobility of 14 and 15, presence of a fleshy and budding mass of about 5*3 cm in diameter occupying the hard palate with extension to the soft palate and the mass having crossed the midline figure (2). On the basis of the clinical elements, we thought of a malignant tumour of the maxilla, probably an adenoid cyst carcinoma (ACC) of the palate. Despite the histological result obtained by the patient, we repeated the biopsy, which confirmed a CAK of the palate after anatomopathological examination. A cervico-facial CT scan was requested and carried out, revealing significant bone lysis of the maxilla with total filling of the right maxillary sinus (Figure 3).

Figure 3a: CT 3D scanning

Figure 3b : CT coronal section scan

Lysis of the right facial bone mass Total filling of the right maxillary sinus An extension work-up was requested: an abdominal ultrasound and a chest X-ray with no particularities. This allowed us to classify the tumour as T4N0M0. The surgical treatment was a hemi maxillectomy (figure 4) plus a maxillofacial obturator prosthesis. (Figure 5) and without lymph node dissection.

Figure 6a: hemi maxillectomy

Figure 6b: operating room

Figure 6c: endo post-op view

The post-operative course was long but good (Figure 6).

Figure 7a: Patient 1 year post-op **Figure 7b: patient with obturator prosthesis at 1 year post-op**

Discussion

The presentation of this clinical case is classically linked to the particular pattern of extension of cystic adenoid carcinomas: the tumour cells have the capacity to infiltrate the nerve sheaths adjacent to the tumour and to spread there. However, these are usually frustrated, which explains the frequent delay in diagnosis. Our patient is male; in the literature there is no equal distribution between the 2 genders, which is corroborated by Bellescu [4]. who found a 60% male predominance, unlike [5]. who found a female predominance with 54.3% of cases. According to the literature, the age most frequently encountered is between the 5th and 6th decade of life [6]. which is consistent with our case. The clinical course of the disease was insidious, with slow growth and often asymptomatic [3]. Our case took 15 years to treat. Dysphonia, dyspnoea and dysphagia without any notion of pain were the main symptoms in our case; [7]. who reported cases of localized pain, i.e. 50% of their series, and localised pain associated with reflex otalgia in the series by Bakouri & Barry [8]. Many authors have emphasised the slow and asymptomatic course of the disease, which is why it is usually diagnosed late. The maxillofacial CT scan in cases of CKD shows a well or poorly limited expansive mass that is usually heterogeneous after injection of the contrast medium [9]. CT scans can be used to look for indirect signs pointing to peri-neural invasion, such as enlargement of the foramen ovale, round foramen and stylomastoid foramen, or abnormal convexity of the lateral wall of the cavernous sinus Bouatey et al. [9]. . It also allows bone lysis to be studied and a precise assessment of locoregional extension to be made. As in our case, the maxillofacial CT scan also revealed lysis of the right maxilla. The treatment of choice remains surgical resection with healthy margins of 0.5 centimetres plus fitting of an obturator prosthesis.

Conclusion

This clinical case shows how difficult it is to diagnose malignant tumours of the assessed salivary glands, mainly adenoid cyst carcinoma of the palate, and the importance of the role of the dental surgeon in diagnosing it.

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